

Neoliberalism and Neocolonialism: A Reading of Indra Sinha's *Animal's People*

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Abstract

Based on the Bhopal industrial disaster of 1984, Indra Sinha's *Animal's People* portrays the terrifying aftermath of one of the worst industrial catastrophes and the subsequent struggle of its inhabitants. The novel captures the intense trauma and enduring loss experienced by the victims, the majority of whom continue to suffer from the physical, emotional, and socio-economic consequences even after nineteen years of the disaster. The novel also delves into the modern forms of colonialism, where powerful corporations exert control over the weaker, leading to exploitation, environmental disaster, and socio-political decay. This paper mainly highlights on the neocolonial power dynamics that play a pivotal role in creating the dystopic Bhopal, where politically fabricated toxicity is more harmful than the literal chemical toxicity caused by the disaster. Additionally, this paper also explores the corporate interests and neoliberal policies that reinforce the neocolonial power structure to create an intensified apparatus of domination and marginalization of vulnerable communities. In brief, this paper brings to the fore how Sinha aims to criticise systemic oppression of the foreign organisation and its dystopian vision of a world where hope remains elusive.

Keywords: Neocolonialism, Neoliberalism, Industrial Disaster, Dystopia.

The gas leak incident in Bhopal from a pesticide plant resulted in the deaths of thousands of inhabitants and left many more with severe chronic health issues. Indra Sinha, as an activist and writer, through his novel *Animal's People*, wanted to give voice to the survivor and highlighted the long-lasting effects of corporate negligence and environmental injustice. *Animal's People* mainly focuses on the physical and psychological effects of the catastrophe on the local community. Sinha also critiques the power dynamics between the government, corporation, and the marginalised community. These power structures particularly mirror the neocolonial strategies where powerful foreign organisations maintain control over developing countries through political and economic influence. This paper delves into the government's role in this tragedy and underscores the neocolonial and neoliberal dynamics of power. In the wake of the disaster, the Indian government, under pressure from international corporate interests, downplayed the scale of the catastrophe and failed to hold Union Carbide

accountable. Neoliberal policies favouring privatization and deregulation made it possible for multinational companies to operate in ways that avoided stringent oversight. As a result, the disaster and its aftermath exemplified how the state, is often complicit in sustaining the power of multinational corporations at the expense of its own citizens. Furthermore, this paper also focuses on the long-term psychological and physical suffering experienced by the survivors of the Bhopal gas leak.

The theoretical framework of this study is grounded in the concepts of neocolonialism and neoliberalism. Neocolonialism is a more subtle process than colonialism, where imperialism has shifted to indirect forces of domination through economic exploitation and control of resources. Kwame Nkrumah states, "Neo-colonialism is based upon the principle of breaking up former large united colonial territories into a number of small non-viable States which are incapable of independent development and rely on former imperial power for defense and even internal security" (Nkrumah, 13). On the other hand, the concept of neoliberalism complements this framework of neocolonialism. Neoliberalism is a set of economic policies and ideologies that promote free-market capitalism, deregulation, privatization of public resources, and a reduced role for the state in managing economic and social welfare. Foucault asserts, "the problem of neo-liberalism was not how to cut out or contrive a free space of the market within an already given political society, as in the liberalism of Adam Smith and the eighteenth century. The problem of neo-liberalism is rather how the overall exercise of political power can be molded on the principles of a market economy. (Foucault, 131)

Based on the fictional town named Khaufpur, which means a village of terror, the story of *Animal's People* centers on the 1984 Bhopal industrial disaster and its effects on the survivors. The story is told from the point of view of a 19-year-old boy who was disfigured that night by the chemical toxicity. Through the protagonist, Animal, the novel depicts the survivors' hopelessness as they fight the organization that continues to exploit them. Through the unfiltered speeches of Animal, the novel represents the tone of the novel, which sometimes depicts plight, disappointments, and sometimes brutality, which ensures the reader's sympathy for the life of Animal, therefore his people, the local inhabitants of Khaufpur. Even after so many years, the terror of "that night" still lingers in the minds of the survivors, even their physical appearances sometimes show what they survived. Animal says, "[p]eople see the outside, but it's inside where the real things happen. No one looks in there; maybe they don't dare" (11). When a foreign journalist calls Animal for an interview, Animal contends, "[f]or his sort, we are not really people. We don't have names. We flit in crowds at the corner of his eye. Extras we're in his movie" (9). It is evident that Animal, in his speeches, expresses a particular opposing mentality and resistance against foreign power, which actually shows anger at being disfigured while he could live a normal life like others if that disaster never happened. Drowning in sorrow, Animal says, "Why did the Kampani choose this city to make its factory?" (32).

The answer Animal is unaware of is a deeply rooted economic structure of countries like India. Countries or regions like India, which are strongly connected to and dependent on the global capitalist system, are stuck in a cycle of underdevelopment. In the case of India,

Achin Vanaik has argued that, “there is no major capitalist country in the third world which has a more powerful state or an indigenous bourgeoisie with more autonomy from foreign capital” (11). India’s dependence on foreign corporations reflects ongoing economic and political dominance by powerful external entities. Multinational corporations often control key sectors of the Indian economy, exploiting cheap labour and natural resources while reaping the majority of profits.

The case against the company had been dragging on for years, sinking in complexities and bureaucratic delays because the company bosses never showed up. Accused of causing the deaths of thousands on that tragic night many years ago, it had become a symbol of unchecked corporate negligence and the enduring struggles of the victims. The tragedy that befell the people of Khaufpur remains one of the most devastating industrial disasters in history, with scars that refuse to heal. Yet, despite overwhelming evidence and persistent advocacy by the affected community, justice remains elusive. Another important character, Nisha, who is involved in the fight of Khaufpur against the company, says to her father, “Maybe you remember such a thing as justice, but in my lifetime there’s been no sign of it” (34).

To compound the suffering, the company abandoned its factory in Khaufpur shortly after the disaster. It left behind a toxic legacy, chemical waste that had seeped into the soil and water over the years. The residents of Khaufpur, already grappling with the long-term health impacts of the gas leak, found themselves battling new illnesses. Families have been torn apart by diseases, birth defects, and respiratory malaises, all linked to the environment they are living in, having no choice but to consume the toxicity. In the novel, a woman who is a mother, while consulting the foreign doctor Elli, says, “Our wells are full of poison. It’s in the soil, water, in our blood, it’s in our milk” (108).

The demands of the Khaufpuris are clear and just. They claim that the company must take full responsibility for its actions. First and foremost, they seek proper compensation for the families of those who lost their lives and for those whose health has been irreparably damaged. Beyond monetary compensation, they demand accountability. But the trouble is that, far away living in Amrika, the company bosses refused to come to court, and no one could make them come. The battle for justice in Khaufpur is not just a local issue. It is a global symbol of the fight against corporate impunity. It raises critical questions about the responsibilities of multinational corporations, the failures of governments to protect their citizens. This represents the ideas of globalization, the term which describes “the world economy has reached a new stage, which governments and workers alike are virtually powerless to withstand” (Harman, 3).

For the past eighteen years, justice has been continuously obstructed due to the absence of the American defendants in court. They remain in Amrika, asserting that the court lacks jurisdiction over them, thereby stalling the legal process. This lack of accountability has led to significant delays, leaving the people of this city who are seeking justice without resolution. As time passes, the prolonged absence of the defendants has caused a serious disruption in the pursuit of justice, where claims remain unaddressed, and victims continue to wait for closure.

The negligence about the case from the respective authority is so clear in the statement of Nisha, who says, "I was four years old when this case began, now it's had thirteen judges" (52). This failure highlights the complexities surrounding jurisdiction in international legal cases. The defendants' claim that the court has no authority to prosecute them reflects a legal tactic used to avoid facing charges. The issue of jurisdiction, particularly in cross-border legal matters, often creates significant obstacles, as the defendants may rely on national sovereignty to evade legal responsibility. The reluctance of the defendants to engage with the court and the continuous deferral of proceedings only deepens the injustice for those seeking resolution. The American corporation's actions reflect the ongoing power imbalance between the global North and the global South, where foreign corporations often escape full liability for their actions in developing countries. The years of legal battles show the difficulties postcolonial states face when confronting powerful multinational corporations that exert significant influence over national affairs, reinforcing the concept of a neocolonial power structure. About the neocolonial power strategies, Nkrumah's assertion that "the state in the grip of neocolonialism is not master of its own destiny" presumes the existence of a strong state which is subjected to control by the former colonies. The theory works at the very center of the state's politics, thus political practices take on a third-worldist or radical-nationalist character. On the other hand, for the people affected, this delay represents more than just a procedural setback. It is a denial of justice. Their rights are compromised, and the legal system's ability to hold the responsible parties accountable is undermined. In the novel, the local activist Zafar says, "[h]ope dies in places like this, because hope lives in the future and there's no future here" (185).

The company has consistently refuted the claims made by survivors, arguing that the alleged health impacts attributed to their operations are exaggerated and unsubstantiated. According to company representatives, the scale of illness reported is not as extensive as claimed, and the severity of health issues among affected individuals has been overstated. They contend that many of the reported illnesses result from pre-existing conditions intensified by widespread poverty, malnutrition, and inadequate sanitation in the region rather than direct exposure to their factory's operations or the events of the night. In defending their stance, the company claims to have taken appropriate measures to ensure safety standards and compliance with regulations, suggesting that the situation has been politicized and sensationalized by activists and media. Moreover, they argue that their presence in the region has contributed positively through job creation and economic opportunities. The denial of liability by the company over the diseases and illnesses caused by the disaster is part of the neocolonial attitude that manufactures systemic inequalities and power imbalance between industrialized nations and the Global South. By blaming the health crises on pre-existing conditions, the company denies the experiences of the affected community and refuses to take responsibility for its actions, much as colonial powers have traditionally profited from the suffering of already vulnerable populations. This denial continues to diminish the voices of local communities while reinforcing injustice, where the postcolonial regions will carry the brunt of environmental degradation and human suffering created by their multinational corporations. These incidents are part of the larger pattern in neocolonialism, in which resource and labor exploitation in the

developing world is cloaked as economic development, and negative impacts obscured or denied by interests.

During a visit by the government-appointed doctress and the foreign doctor Elli to a slum affected by the disaster, tensions flared when a woman, convinced that her breast milk was toxic, poured it onto the ground in despair. Her act was a stark expression of fear and helplessness, symbolizing the community's deep anxiety about contamination. Instead of addressing the woman's concerns or offering comfort, the doctress reacted harshly. She snapped at the woman and said, "How many times have I told you not to believe rumours?" (107) This incident reveals a significant gap between the survivors' experiences and the authorities' approach to managing their concerns. It is also evident that the government is indirectly supporting the company and hiding their guilt. The governments in the neocolonial power structure have to rely on private companies because they are economically dependent on them. This is a basic tendency of underdeveloped countries that believe development comes through privatization.

The night the poisons escaped from the company's factory marked a turning point in the lives of the community. Those who survived the immediate disaster were left battling horrific symptoms of fainting, fits, pain, coughing blood, blindness, and difficulty in breathing. In this context of widespread suffering, people came to know of a treatment offering relief. The "thighs-of-fate," or Sodium Thiosulphate, the locally developed medicine offering relief to survivors of the poison leak, became a symbol of hope amidst despair. News of the "thighs-of-fate" spread rapidly, and people from across the city queued for injections that could alleviate their misery. However, this hope was short-lived, as the treatment was suddenly and inexplicably halted. The efficacy of the "thighs-of-fate" posed a threat to the company's narrative of denial and obfuscation. If the treatment's success became widely known, it could establish a direct link between the poisons and the community's suffering, undermining the company's legal defenses. This fear of exposure underscores the neocolonial tendency to suppress truth to preserve power. As Zafar said, "The Kampani was afraid of this knowledge getting out because it might cost them in a court case, so they had the thighs-of-fate stopped and many were lost who could have been saved" (112). The suspension of the medicine, allegedly at the behest of the company's American bosses, who reportedly pressured their ally, the Chief Minister, to stop its distribution, underscores the pervasive influence of corporate power in postcolonial contexts. Sinha's portrayal of this incident brings out the human cost of neocolonialism. The Survivors, first victimized by the factory's negligence, are now marginalized as their access to Life-saving treatment is denied. This is the working of corporate greed and the complicity of Politics in systematic injustice, reflecting the bigger critique of how the neocolonial structures Beget inequality. In *Animal's People*, the tragedy of the community is but a microcosm of the Global dynamics of exploitation in which the powerful make profits at the cost of lives, and Subalterns bear the brunt of their actions.

The opening of the clinic of Elli doctress with the help of the Poison Relief Minister also Reflects the dynamics of NGO-ization in a neoliberal global order. In this scenario, an "Amrikan Woman" appears in Khaufpur to establish a clinic, described by Zafar as a "so-called

clinic.” This act, while superficially charitable, is embedded within a larger framework of neoliberal Policies and practices that characterize the NGO-ization of social services in the Global South. This process often reflects the withdrawal of state responsibility and the growing role of nongovernmental organizations in addressing social needs. Feher said, “Liberal critics celebrate the Ability of NGOs to act in areas of ‘defective governance’ (25).”

NGO-ization refers to the increasing reliance on NGOs to provide essential services, often in contexts where state institutions have been weakened or dismantled. This phenomenon is Closely linked to neoliberalism, a political and economic ideology emphasizing free markets, privatization, and reduced government intervention in social welfare. Under neoliberal policies, States are often encouraged or coerced by global financial institutions to limit public expenditure And privatize essential services. As a result, NGOs step in to fill the gaps left by the retreating State, often funded by international donors or foreign governments.

In the novel, the clinic’s establishment reflects these dynamics. The involvement of a Foreign doctor, described as performing a “wonderful act of charity,” underscores the dependence on external interventions to address local crises. Such initiatives are typically lauded in neoliberal discourse as efficient, innovative, and community-oriented alternatives to state-run services. However, Zafar’s skepticism, “what is its real purpose?” captures the underlying Tensions and contradictions of NGO-ization. This skepticism reflects local concerns about whether the clinic serves genuine community needs or operates as a tool for advancing donordriven agendas. The role of local politicians, such as Zahreel Khan, the Minister for Poison Relief, further highlights the entanglement of NGO initiatives with neoliberal governance. Rather than Addressing systemic issues or ensuring public accountability, the minister’s involvement suggests that such initiatives may become symbolic gestures tied to political self-promotion. This aligns with neoliberal practices where the state functions as a facilitator of private or non-state actors rather than as a provider of welfare. Moreover, the media’s framing of the clinic as a charitable act, as noted in the Khaufpur Gazette, reflects how neoliberalism commodifies and celebrates philanthropy while neglecting structural inequalities.

In another event, Elli, the doctress, embarks on an intense confrontation with the Minister, Zahreel Khan. The minister indicates the sustaining forces underlying Khaufpur’s suffering, hinting that activists have a vested interest in maintaining Khaufpur as a “tragedy.” When Elli wonders why her clinic meets opposition when it seeks only to better the situation, he rebukes her idealism with cynicism, informing her that the bureaucratic and cultural chains of Khaufpur stonewall her efforts. He further alludes to the incompatibility of her work with local systems, citing bureaucratic delays and cultural norms, such as the idea that a woman operating independently in a foreign country is an unheard-of thing. These remarks frame the situation as a clash between Elli’s humanitarian goals and systemic forces that resist meaningful change. In this event, the minister represents a neocolonial framework wherein Khaufpur’s dependency on foreign aid has come to mirror the legacy of colonial control. The dismissal of Elli’s clinic as an idealistic effort underscores the idea that local or regional efforts are inherently ineffective, a hallmark of neocolonialism. This erodes local agency by framing

Khauipur as incapable of self-sufficiency which ensures that external forces retain control over the narrative and resources. The minister's allusion to cultural norms and bureaucracy draws on orientalist tropes, painting Khauipur as retrogressive and anarchic while the West is rational and orderly. Such dynamics undermine the potential for local empowerment, maintaining Khauipur as a site of external intervention and control. Other than addressing systemic issues, the suffering in Khauipur becomes a resource to sustain financial and foreign interest. Elli's reliance on permissions and the minister's lack of support reflect a system that shifts responsibility for social change onto private actors, such as philanthropists or NGOs, rather than addressing structural inequalities. This individualistic solution, so characteristic of neoliberal values, turns away from Any long-term systemic reform and toward profit-based short-term fixes. Put together, the event underlines the junction of neocolonial and neoliberal dynamics. Neocolonialism keeps Khauipur in its state of dependency and marginalization, while neoliberalism commodifies its suffering and shifts the burden of change onto external actors to Ensure the persistence of both systemic inequality and exploitation.

Thus the novel does more than critique the historical aftermath of the Bhopal disaster; it uncovers the insidious mechanisms of marginalization and domination that operate in contemporary global contexts. It stresses how corporate interests and neoliberal agendas continue to shape the experiences of impoverished and disenfranchised communities, especially in postcolonial settings where power structures remain rooted in the legacies of colonialism. Through the mirror of the disaster in Khauipur, the novel places at center stage the means by which transnational capital, enabled by collusive states and failing regulatory regimes, establishes a new colonialism one powered not by geographical expansion but by market penetration, economic appropriation, and human dispensability.

This paper is relevant to current social issues, particularly because the struggle against corporate irresponsibility and environmental injustice has continued unabated. The resonance of the fictional case of Animal's People to real-world cases of corporate exploitation, especially in the Global South, testifies to the persistence of these concerns. Results from this study, therefore, speak to the urgent need for accountability in the face of corporate negligence and the continued exploitation of vulnerable populations. In a broader context, this study is related to the international debate on sustainable development, corporate responsibility, and social equity.

Works Cited

Chossudovsky, Michel. *The Globalization of Poverty and the New World Order*. Global Research, Center for Research on Globalization(CRG), 2003.

Feher, Michel. *Nongovernmental Politics*. Princeton University Press, 2007.

Harvey, David. *A Brief History of Neoliberalism*. Oxford University Press Inc., 2005.

Nkrumah , Kwame. *Neo-Colonialism*. Thomas Nelson & Sons, Ltd., 1965.

Rao, Nagesh. "'Neocolonialism' or 'Globalization'?: Postcolonial Theory and the Demands of Political Economy Author(S)." *Interdisciplinary Literary Studies*, vol. 1, no. 2, 2000, pp. 165–84.

Sinha, Indra. *Animal's People*. Simon & Schuster UK Ltd, 2007.

Steger, Manfred B., and Ravi K. Roy. *Neoliberalism: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press Inc., 2010.

Zayed, Sarker Hasan Al. *Allegories of Neoliberalism*. Routledge, 2023.

---. "Allegorizing Neoliberalism: Contemporary South Asian Fictions and the Critique of Capitalism." *CROSSINGS: Special Volume on Marx 200*, 2020, pp. 117–36.